

Datum 15 april 2024

Titel: Impulse Open Science Communities-NL

Beste John Doove,

Referenten hebben uw bovengenoemde projectvoorstel beoordeeld op basis van de criteria zoals beschreven in de uitnodigingsbrief van Open Science NL van 25 januari 2024. U heeft nu de mogelijkheid om een weerwoord te schrijven op deze referentenrapporten. Open Science NL legt uw weerwoord samen met de referentenrapporten en het projectvoorstel voor aan de stuurgroep van Open Science NL. Open Science NL deelt je weerwoord niet met de referenten.

Deadline voor het weerwoord

U krijgt vijf werkdagen de tijd om te reageren op de rapporten van de referenten. De deadline voor het verzenden van uw weerwoord via een e-mail naar openscience@nwo.nl is 23 april 2024 14:00 CET.

Als uw weerwoord niet voor de aangegeven deadline is ontvangen, wordt deze niet opgenomen in de rest van de procedure.

Instructie voor het schrijven van het weerwoord

- Uw weerwoord moet in het Engels zijn geschreven en mag niet meer dan 2 pagina's (A4) bevatten (Calibri, maat 10).
- Gelieve geen bijlagen in te dienen.
- Reageer bij het schrijven van het weerwoord direct op de inhoud van de referentenrapporten (onder vermelding van reviewer 1 en/of 2).
- Blijf zo neutraal mogelijk en geef beknopte antwoorden waarin u uitlegt of en hoe u van plan bent de door de referenten genoemde aandachtspunten of problemen aan te pakken. Als u het niet eens bent met een van de uitspraken van de referenten, leg dan uit waarom dit het geval is.

Generatieve AI

Het gebruik van generatieve AI-tools, zoals ChatGPT, is [momenteel niet toegestaan gedurende het hele beoordelingsproces](#). Alle documenten die ter beoordeling worden voorgelegd aan referenten, commissieleden of juryleden zijn vertrouwelijk en onderworpen aan geheimhoudingsverplichtingen. Daarom mogen er geen documenten uit het beoordelingsproces worden ingevoerd in generatieve AI-tools.

DORA en NWO

De Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek (NWO) heeft [DORA](#) ondertekend. DORA is een wereldwijd initiatief dat tot doel heeft de afhankelijkheid van bibliometrische indicatoren (zoals publicaties en citaties) bij de evaluatie van onderzoek en onderzoekers te verminderen. In de geest van deze verklaring vragen wij u om reputatiebeschrijvingen van tijdschriften en citatiescores (zoals Journal Impact Factors en H-index) achterwege te laten in uw weerwoord. Meer informatie vindt u hier: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/dora>

Aarzel niet om contact met ons op te nemen als u vragen heeft. Contactgegevens staan hieronder vermeld.

Met vriendelijke groet,

Jeroen Sondervan

Programmaleider Open Scholarly COmmunication

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Rebuttal to the reviewer's comments

Concrete and realistic project plan

- We would like to thank reviewer 1 and 2 for their positive evaluation of our project plan. We are pleased to hear that they see the added benefit of SURF as a host organisation (reviewer 1) and that the work packages are comprehensive and the deliverables compelling (reviewer 2).
- Reviewer 1 is very positive about the OSC Toolkit and asks whether OSC managers will have enough time to attend the OSC incubator program when they are fulfilling their role on a voluntary basis. We intend to offer the OSC incubator program to those OSC managers who are reimbursed for their time, as a result of the Open Science NL impulse for local OSCs (or institutional investments), as reviewer 1 suggests.
- We have taken note of the concern expressed by Reviewer 1 concerning the time-hungry nature of developing communication resources. The reviewer notes that the allocated effort in 3.1 may be too low. Please note that in addition to the effort allocated to this WP, we have also allocated budget to outsource the design and production of printed and online materials to a professional.
- Reviewer 1 suggest to start earlier with the development of the sustainability plan (4.2.2, 4.2.3). We will indeed not wait for year 3 to take actions on this. However, in the first years, our activities will be mainly focussed on liasing with stakeholder to monitor how the 16 signatories of the OpenScienceNL are following-up on their agreement to strengthen local OSCs. In the second half of the project, it will be more clear what is required to sustain the OSC-NL network, which is why we have planned the development of the sustainability plan in the second half of the project.
- Reviewer 2 comments that the first two years of the project more resource intensive compared to the last two years. This is indeed correct, as for example the development of the OSC Toolkit (1.1.1, 2.1, 3.1, 4.2.1) and the Governance model (4.1) are planned early on in the project. The reviewer is concerned whether we have enough resources to deliver what we have planned in this period. In response, it is good to nite that have planned our tasks in accordance with the available resources. In particular, the involvement of Melanie Imming will be focussed on the first half of the project (she will be less active in the second half of the project).

Team composition

- We are pleased to hear that Reviewer 2 deems our ET highly qualified and committed to carrying our the work.
- Reviewer 1 asks what the process was by which the ET members were selected. The team members have been selected by the OSC-NL board, based on their expertise and availability. The OSC-NL board has formally approved the composition of the ET, in consultation with the OSC-NL managers. The ET members have confirmed their availability for the duration of the project.
- Reviewers 1 comments on the high level of financial responsibility of the tasks in which Rianne Fijten is involved. Please note these task (as all tasks) are group efforts of the ET and the relevant expertise is available in the team.
- Reviewer 2 asks how decision processes are organised internally in the ET and how the ET will interact with the OSC-NL Board. The ET is indeed a collaborative team of equals. In the case of disagreements within the ET, the OSC-NL Board will decide on the appropriate course of action. Loek Brinkman and Rianne Fijten will resign as board members at the moment they join the Executive Team.

Relevant target groups and resources

- We are pleased to hear that Reviewer 1 acknowledges the importance of our planned mechanisms to embed systems and processes to assist with the onboarding of new people in their role as OSC manager.
- Reviewer 1 asks for a contingency plan for the preservation of developed materials, for when we are unsuccessful in acquiring subsequent funding at the end of this project. All materials that will be developed as part of this project will be openly shared within the network of OSCs. As such, in the case that subsequent funding will not be acquired, local OSCs can continue to use and maintain our materials. We would like to stress that the scenario that subsequent funding is not available, neither at the national level nor at the local level, is highly unlikely, as the 16 signatories of the OpenScienceNL covenant have committed to work towards the sustainability of the OSC-NL network.
- Reviewer 1 notes that the travel budget for the ET might be too low. We do not expect a large overspend on this budget as we don't foresee a need for hotel stays (as Reviewer 1 mentioned). Nevertheless, we follow the suggestion of Reviewer 1 and re-evaluate this budget in relation to the reimbursement fund for external period.
- Reviewer 2 notes that while our plans to increase the visibility and findability within our network are solid, our plans for reaching beyond the people already involved in the network. We would like to stress that the OSC-NL Board and ET focus on interacting with stakeholders at the national level, but will not focus on directly interacting with researchers – this is the responsibility of local OSCs. We will assist local OSCs to become more successful in this regard, e.g. with the OSC Toolkit, but the local OSCs should remain the first point of contact for researchers to join or interact with their local OSC.

Organisational embedding and sustainability

- We are pleased to hear that locating the ET at SURF contributes greatly to the organisational embedding of the team.
- Reviewer 2.2.1 would like to have more information regarding the frequency of the knowledge exchange sessions. As noted in deliverable 2.2.1., we will organise these knowledge exchange sessions 2 times per year.
- As noted by Reviewer 2, the models for sustainability for the ET have not been worked out yet. Indeed, as Reviewer 2 notes, the first two years of the project will provide us the information needed to further explore the most appropriate course of action.

Summary of the assessment

- We are pleased to hear that both reviewers regard our proposal more than sufficient to receive funding. The work plan and team are regarded as solid and strong (Reviewer 2) and the activities proposed are in line with the outcome sought by the project (Reviewer 1). In addition, we are very pleased to hear the Dutch approach to OSC can be an example for other national and groups to build upon (Reviewer 2).

